

Long-term data for Europe

EURHISFIRM

D2.5: Presentations of the project at events and conferences

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I. Introduction

The strategic goal of Work Package 2 (WP2 - Dissemination & Communication) was the active communication and dissemination of knowledge about the EURHISFIRM project among the widest possible audience.

WP2's main tasks included:

- Developing the project's identity and brand
- Developing of a dissemination and communication plan
- Creating an inventory of European and national distribution networks

In the first year of the EURHISFIRM project, prior to the COVID-19 global pandemic, the intended goals progressed perfectly according to the planned schedule. It managed to complete the following deliverables and milestones¹:

- Deliverables:
 - D2.1 Dissemination and communication plan (M2)
 - D2.2 Website and project identity (M4)
 - D2.3 Inventory of European and national distribution networks (M6)
- Milestones:
 - M2.1 Dissemination and communication plan (M2)
 - M2.2 Project website (M4)

After this successful first year, WP2 was left to work on the last two deliverables D2.4: Involvement of new stakeholders as participants to the General Assembly (M36) and **D2.5: Presentations of the project at events and conferences (M36)**.

II. External outreach

The main objective of D2.5 was to disseminate and communicate the EURHISFIRM project with the intended purpose of promoting its visibility and long-term success. Given the imposed restriction on personal contact, as a consequence of the COVID-19 worldwide pandemic, many events were either postponed, cancelled or held online. This meant that a creative use of alternative means of communication was required to ensure the further outreach of the EURHISFIRM project.

2.1. Website and social networking sites

One of the most important tools of external communication for the project proved to be (I.) the website (<https://eurhisfirm.eu>), but also (II.) other online platforms and (specialized) social networking sites, including Facebook, ResearchGate, LinkedIn and Twitter:

¹ D1.10

- I. The website devoted to the EURHISFIRM project mainly includes the work of individual WP teams. Regularly published information allows stakeholders to observe the activities and progress of the project. It is a key aspect in terms of achieving the aforementioned strategic goal, but also a tool to encourage further interest in the EURHISFIRM project. In addition, the website contains descriptions and contacts to people directly related to the project, which makes it easier for interested parties to reach decision-makers in a specific area.
- II. The active use of the potential of social networking sites allowed EURHISFIRM to reach out to external stakeholders and other interested parties. The selection of the social networking sites most appropriate to the information provided allowed to strengthen the overall philosophy of the EURHISFIRM project.

Cooperation with partner projects and institutions, such as SSHOC and CESSDA ERIC, which assisted in the online promotion of EURHISFIRM, made it possible to reach out to an even wider audience. The esteemed reputation of these partner projects contributed to the positive strengthening of the EURHISFIRM “brand”.

A non-exhaustive overview of the (online) dissemination of information by CESSDA ERIC includes:

- a) Twitter: Tweet on CESSDA presentation at project Kick-off (https://twitter.com/CESSDA_Data/status/1106593700128403458) (Impressions 514; engagements 20); Mar 15, 2019
- b) Website:
 - Presenting EURHISFIRM project on CESSDA webpage (<https://www.cessda.eu/About/Projects/offset/5> and <https://www.cessda.eu/About/Projects/Current-projects/EURHISFIRM>) January 2021
 - News piece on EURHISFIRM joining SSHOC on SSHOC project website: (<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/eurhisfirm-joins-sshoc-partner-consortium>), 18 Sept 2020
 - Presenting EURHISFIRM project on SSHOC project website: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/partners/eurhisfirm>; 18 Sept 2020
 - Article on EURHISFIRM on CESSDA website: <https://www.cessda.eu/News-Events/News/CESSDA/CESSDA-ERIC-joins-the-EURHISFIRM-project>, 11 Dec 2020
- c) Annual report. CESSDA Annual Report 2020 - Item on EURHISFIRM in Section “EC Projects” (in publication) - will be available here: <https://www.cessda.eu/News-Events/Annual-Reports>

2.2. Presentation of the project at events and conferences

Despite the COVID-19 worldwide pandemic, the EURHISFIRM project was actively promoted at the following events:

1. The Session at the World Economic History Conference planned in 2021 is postponed to 2022. <https://wehc2021.sciencesconf.org/>
2. A workshop on “The Price of Everything, But the Value of Nothing” under the auspices of EURHISFIRM, Amsterdam, 27 November 2020
3. 4th Consortium meeting of the SSHOC, 8th and 9th September 2020, EURHISFIRM was presented after joining the SSHOC project

4. Presentation at the 2020 Business History Conference. Charlotte, North Carolina, 12-14 of March 2020, by Christopher Coyle, Robin Adams "The Wee Divergence: Entrepreneurship and Political Turmoil in Ireland Before 1900"
5. CLARIN coordination meeting, virtual, on April 7th, 2021 (after a first meeting Jan 15th, 2021 was cancelled)
6. Presentations made by Angelo Riva who presented the Project:
 - a. Hommage à Georges Gallais-Hamou, Online, 5th of October 2020.
Riva A., From GGH to Eurhisfirm. The 'Big Data Revolution' in financial history. Some experiments
 - b. Conseil Supérieur des Archives, Ministère de la Culture, Paris, 11th of December 2019.
Laperdrix M., Riva A., L'Exploitation "Big data" des Archives de la Compagnie des Agents de change de Paris.
 - c. Data for Financial History Workshop
Paris, 13th of December 2018.
Paris School of Economics, Riva A., Eurhisfirm.
 - d. Les archives, patrimoine et richesse de l'action publique, 2ème Rencontre du réseau archives des ministères économiques et financiers, Paris, Bercy, 10 th of April 2018.
Riva A., The "Big data" Revolution in Financial History. Some experiments".
 - e. EABH (European Association of Banking and Financial History) Workshop "The data dilemma: a risk or an asset?" (joint event with INFUTURE 2017 International Conference "Integrating ICT in Society"), Zagreb (Croatia), 8-10 of November 2017.
Riva A., "The 'Big Data Revolution' in banking and financial history? The French Experiments: Successes, Failures and Developments
7. Prepared a poster to promote the EURHISFIRM project at the Conference of the Verein für Sozialpolitik in Regensburg. Hanna Floto-Degener was presented with the poster.
Mobility and Migration in Historical Perspective III. Congress for Economic and Social History 20 - 22 of March 2019.
8. EURHISFIRM project information during the onsite evaluations at SAFE held in the past years (for entering the Leibniz Association). Since 2020 SAFE has been a member institute of the Leibniz Association, which is a union of 96 German non-university research institutes. The Leibniz Institutes cooperate closely with universities and are funded publicly by the federal government and the federal states (total budget of €1.9 billion).
9. Presentation by CESSDA ERIC (Prepared by: Martina Drasci, Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Ron Dekker):
 - 13th CESSDA Service Providers' Forum, Bergen, 10 October 2019 - agenda item 13.08 Reports and Information from Main Office announcing CESSDA joining EURHISFIRM project (internal use only, not public)
 - 6th CESSDA General assembly, Copenhagen, 21 November 2019 - agenda item 6.06d Report from Main Office - EC projects on amendment aiming to add CESSDA to EURHISFIRM consortium
 - 14th CESSDA Service Providers' Forum, virtual, 7 April 2020 - agenda item 14.08 European issues, including EC projects overview (internal use only, not public)
 - Announcing EURHISFIRM project and members joining SSHOC project (SSHOC 2nd Consortium meeting, Florence, 14 Oct 2020, WP1 presentation, Martina Drascic - internal project use only, not public);

- Introducing EURHISFIRM project and members to join to the SSHOC Strategic Board (SSHOC 2nd Consortium meeting - Strategic Board pre-meeting, Florence, 14 Oct 2020, Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Ron Dekker - internal use only, not public);
- 8th CESSDA General Assembly, virtual, 24 November 2020 - agenda item 08.07 Report from Director/MO, EC projects overview (internal use only, not public)
- 16th CESSDA Service Providers' Forum, virtual, 15 April 2021 - agenda item 16.09 EC projects and CESSDA (overview, internal use only, not public)

Future promotional activities are scheduled, especially now that the COVID-19 restrictions are gradually being lifted. This includes a presentation at ICTeSSH2021 held on the 29th of June 2021, where the milestone of WP5 will be presented. This presentation is titled "An Extensible Model for Historical Financial Data with an Application to German Company and Stock Market Data", by: Dennis Gram, Pantelis Karapanagiotis, Jan Krzyzanowski, Marius Liebald and Uwe Walz. More presentations will surely follow.

III. Conclusion

The COVID-19 led to postponement, or outright cancellation of many events and conferences. However, in spite of these challenges, the project proceeded successfully and managed to extend its outreach. It did so by relying on the EURHISFIRM website and via social networking sites, but also via presentations at various events and conferences that did take place. In the end, information about the project has been successfully delivered to over 190 external stakeholders and partners, spread across over Europe, in 11 different countries.